

Profitability Performance of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd

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Profit serves as a yard stick for judging the competence and efficiency of the management. Profit determines the financial position, Liquidity and solvency of the company. Therefore, profit planning is a fundamental part of the overall management function and is an important part of the total budgeting process. The main objective of any business organisations to earn profit. The term profitability refers to an indication of the efficiency with which of the operation of the business is carried on. A poor operational performance may lead to lower profitability. Lower profitability may rise due to lack of control over the expenses. The bankers, financial institutions, Cooperative credit Societies and other creditors consider profitability ratio as an indicator to take major decisions.

Objectives of the Study

1. To analyse the factors affecting profitability of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd.
2. To offer suitable suggestions on the basis of finding of the study.

Methodology

The “Case study Method” has been adopted to achieve the cited above objectives of the study. The study is purely based on the secondary data and it has been collected from the Annual Reports of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd, Government publications, Books, Journals, Websites are the major source of secondary data.

Period of the Study

The study covers a period of Five years from 2011 to 2015.

Tools used for Analysis

In order to analyses the profit and profitability position of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd, ratio analysis has been used.

The analysis is made with the help of standard financial ratios, Growth Rate and Co-efficient of Correlation.

Analysis and Discussions

Ratio analysis is used to analyze the Sustainable Economic Development of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd. Further it gives the information to take decisions for planning and control of activities of the Bank . This analysis enables one to identify the nature and causes of changes in profits and profitability over the period of time and this helps in pinpointing the direction of action required for altering the prospects of the Bank in future.

In order to analyse the profitability performance of George Town Cooperative Bank the following ratios have been used.

- Net profit to total assets
- Interest income to total assets
- Other income to total assets
- Total income to total assets
- Net profit to total advances
- Interest income to Total advances

Net Profit to Total Assets Ratio of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd.,

TABLE 1 Shows Net Profit to Total Assets ratio of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd.,

**Table 1 Net Profit to Total Assets ratio of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd.,
(Rs in Crores)**

Year	Net profit	Total assets	Net profit/total assets (%)
2011	1.06	204.66	0.52%
2012	1.09	233.96	0.49%
2013	1.12	26.47	0.43%
2014	1.07	289.97	0.37%
2015	1.36	292.81	0.46%

Source: George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd., Annual Report

From the Table 1, it is understood that the ratio of net profit to total assets is ranged between 0.37 per cent and 0.52 per cent during the study period. It is also shows that the net profit to total assets ratio was less than 1.00 per cent in all the year.

Interest Income To Total Assets Ratio Of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd.,

Table 2 Shows Interest Income to Total Assets ratio George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd.,

**Table 2 Interest Income to Total Assets Ratio of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd.,
(Rs in Crores)**

Year	Interest income	Total assets	Interest income /total assets (%)
2011	18.55	204.66	9.06%
2012	20.66	223.96	8.95%
2013	24.66	260.47	9.467%
2014	28.69	289.97	9.9%
2015	29.61	292.81	10.11%

Source: George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd., Annual Report

The Table 2 reveals that the interest income of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd was Rs. 18.55 crores in 2011 and Rs. 29.61 in 2015. The ratio of interest income to Total assets was 8.95 per cent in 2012 and 10.11 per cent in 2015 during the study period.

Other Income to Total Assets of George Town Cooperative Bank

Table 3 Shows Other Income to Total Assets of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd.,

Table 3 Other Income to Total Assets of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd., (Rs in Crores)

Year	Other income	Total assets	Other income/total assets (%)
2011	0.25	204.66	0.12%
2012	0.25	223.96	0.11%
2013	0.28	260.47	0.10%
2014	0.32	289.97	0.11%
2015	0.49	292.81	0.16%

Source: George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd., Annual Report

The above table 3 explains the proportion of other income to total assets of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd was 0.10 per cent in the year 2013 and 0.16 per cent in the year 2015. The other income of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd was Rs.0.25 crores in 2012 and Rs. 0.49 crores in 2015.

Total Income To Total Assets of George Town Cooperative Bank

Table 4 Shows Total Incomes to Total Assets of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd.,

Table 4 Total Incomes to Total Assets of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd., (Rs in Crores)

Year	Total income	Total assets	Total income/total assets (%)
2011	18.55	204.66	9.06%
2012	20.06	223.96	8.95%
2013	24.66	260.47	9.47%
2014	28.69	289.97	9.9%
2015	29.61	292.81	10.11%

Source: George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd., Annual Report

It is observed from the Table 4 that the total incomes of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd were increased from Rs.18.55 crores in 2011 and Rs.29.61 crores in 2015. The ratio of total income to total assets was 8.95 per cent in the year 2012 and 10.11 per cent in the year 2015.

Net Profit To Total Advances Of George Town Cooperative Bank

Table 5 Net Profit To Total Advances of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd., (Rs in Crores)

Year	Net Profit	Total Advance	Net Profit / Total Advances (%)
2011	1.06	118.39	0.89%
2012	1.09	141.04	0.77%

2013	1.12	164.90	0.67%
2014	1.07	163.09	0.65%
2015	1.36	140.59	0.97%

Source: George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd., Annual Report

Table 5 highlights the ratio of net profit to total advances which was 0.65 per cent in 2014 and 0.97 per cent in 2015. The total advances of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd have increased from Rs. 118.39 crores in 2011 to Rs.140.59 crores in 2015.

Interest Income to Total Advances of George Town Cooperative Bank

Table 6 Interest Income to Total Advances of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd., (Rs in Crores)

Year	Interest Income	Total Advances	Interest Income / Total Advances (%)
2011	18.55	118.39	15.67%
2012	20.06	141.04	14.22%
2013	24.66	164.90	14.95%
2014	28.69	163.09	17.59%
2015	29.61	140.59	21.06%

Source: George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd., Annual Report

It is observed from the Table 6 that the interest incomes of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd were increased from Rs.18.55 crores in 2011 and Rs.29.61 crores in 2015. The ratio of interest income to total advances was 14.22 per cent in the year 2012 and 21.06 per cent in the year 2015.

Correlation

Correlation is the relationship between the two variables. The economic quantities variables presented and are compared to the profitability of the George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd over the years understudy. The formula for the technique of correlation Co-efficient is

$$\frac{\sum dx dy}{N \sqrt{\sum dx^2 \sum dy^2}}$$

$$r = \frac{\sum dx dy}{N \sqrt{\sum dx^2 \sum dy^2}}$$

$$\sum dx^2 - (\sum dx)^2 = \sum dy^2 - (\sum dy)^2$$

$$NN$$

Correlation Technique is used by the researcher in this study to ascertain the Interest earned and Profitability. The term interest earned means the income derived by advancing the sources of funds prudently. Interest earning is the main source of income as for as the George Town Cooperative Bank in India is concerned. Table 4.7 shows the Correlation between interest earned and Profit of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd.

Table 7 Correlation between Interest Earned and Net Profit (Rs in Crores)

Year	Interest Earned	Net Profit	Dx	Dx ²	Dy	Dy ²	DxDy
2011	18.55	1.06	-6.11	37.33	-0.06	0.0036	0.37
2012	20.66	1.09	-4	16	-0.03	0.0009	0.12
2013	24.66	1.12	0	0	0	0	0
2014	28.69	1.07	4.03	16.24	-0.05	0.0025	-0.20

2015	29.61	1.36	4.95	24.50	0.24	0.0576	1.19
			$\Sigma dx =$ -1.13	$\Sigma dx^2 =$ 94.07	$\Sigma dy =$ 0.1	$\Sigma dy^2 =$ 0.0646	$\Sigma dx dy =$ 1.48

$$\Sigma dx dy - (\Sigma dx) (\Sigma dy)$$

$$r = \frac{\Sigma dx dy - (\Sigma dx) (\Sigma dy)}{N \sqrt{\Sigma dx^2 - (\Sigma dx)^2 + \Sigma dy^2 - (\Sigma dy)^2}}$$

$$NN$$

$$r = -0.037$$

It could be seen from the above calculation that there is a highly positive Correlation between interest earned and profitability.

Table 8 Correlation between Total Income and Net Profit (Rs in Crores)

Year	Interest Expenditure	Net Profits	Dx	Dx ²	Dy	Dy ²	DxDy
2011	11.42	1.06	-5.49	30.14	-0.06	0.0036	0.33
2012	13.31	1.09	-3.6	12.96	-0.03	0.0009	0.11
2013	16.91	1.12	0	0	0	0	0
2014	20.63	1.07	3.72	13.84	-0.05	0.0025	-0.19
2015	22.20	1.36	5.29	29.98	0.24	0.0576	1.27
			$\Sigma dx =$ -0.08	$\Sigma dx^2 =$ 86.92	$\Sigma dy =$ 0.1	$\Sigma dy^2 =$ 0.0646	$\Sigma dx dy =$ 1.52

Source: Source: RBI Report on Trend and Progress of banking in India

$$\Sigma dx dy - (\Sigma dx) (\Sigma dy)$$

$$r = \frac{\Sigma dx dy - (\Sigma dx) (\Sigma dy)}{N \sqrt{\Sigma dx^2 - (\Sigma dx)^2 + \Sigma dy^2 - (\Sigma dy)^2}}$$

$$NN$$

$$r = -0.048$$

It could be seen from the above calculation that there is a Moderate degree of negative Correlation between total interest and profitability.

Table 8 Correlation between Interest Expenditure and Net Profit (Rs in Crores)

Year	Interest Expenditure	Net Profits	Dx	Dx ²	Dy	Dy ²	DxDy
2011	11.42	1.06	-5.49	30.14	-0.06	0.0036	0.33
2012	13.31	1.09	-3.6	12.96	-0.03	0.0009	0.11
2013	16.91	1.12	0	0	0	0	0
2014	20.63	1.07	3.72	13.84	-0.05	0.0025	-0.19
2015	22.20	1.36	5.29	29.98	0.24	0.0576	1.27
			$\Sigma dx =$ -0.08	$\Sigma dx^2 =$ 86.92	$\Sigma dy =$ 0.1	$\Sigma dy^2 =$ 0.0646	$\Sigma dx dy =$ 1.52

$$\Sigma dx dy - (\Sigma dx) (\Sigma dy)$$

$$r = \frac{\Sigma dx dy - (\Sigma dx) (\Sigma dy)}{N \sqrt{\Sigma dx^2 - (\Sigma dx)^2 + \Sigma dy^2 - (\Sigma dy)^2}}$$

$$NN$$

$$r = -0.002$$

It could be seen from the above calculation that there is a low degree of negative Correlation between Interest expenditure and profitability.

Table 9 Correlation Between Total Expenditure And Net Profit Rs in Crores)

Year	Total Expenditure	Net Profits	Dx	Dx ²	Dy	Dy ²	DxDy
2011	16.74	1.06	-7.07	49.99	-0.06	0.0036	0.42
2012	19.22	1.09	-4.59	21.07	-0.03	0.0009	0.14
2013	23.81	1.12	0	0	0	0	0
2014	21.15	1.07	-2.66	7.07	-0.05	0.0025	0.13
2015	23.1	1.36	-0.71	0.50	0.24	0.0576	-0.17
			$\Sigma dx =$ -15.03	$\Sigma dx^2 =$ 78.63	$\Sigma dy =$ 0.1	$\Sigma dy^2 =$ 0.0646	$\Sigma dx dy =$ 0.52

Source: RBI Report on Trend and Progress of banking in India

$\Sigma dx dy - (\Sigma dx)(\Sigma dy)$

$r = \frac{\Sigma dx dy - (\Sigma dx)(\Sigma dy)}{N \sqrt{(\Sigma dx^2 - (\Sigma dx)^2 / N)(\Sigma dy^2 - (\Sigma dy)^2 / N)}}$

N

$r = -0.83$

It could be seen from the above calculation that there is a high degree of negative Correlation between total expenditure and profitability.

Summary of Findings

- The ratio of net profit to total assets is ranged between 0.37 per cent and 0.52 per cent during the study period. It also shows that the net profit to total assets ratio was less than 1.00 per cent in all the year.
- The interest income of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd was Rs. 18.55 crores in 2011 and Rs. 29.61 in 2015. The ratio of interest income to Total assets was 8.95 per cent in 2012 and 10.11 per cent in 2015 during the study period.
- The proportion of other income to total assets of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd was 0.10 per cent in the year 2013 and 0.16 per cent in the year 2015. The other income of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd was Rs.0.25 crores in 2012 and Rs. 0.49 crores in 2015.
- The total incomes of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd were increased from Rs.18.55 crores in 2011 and Rs.29.61 crores in 2015. The ratio of total income to total assets was 8.95 percent in the year 2012 and 10.11 per cent in the year 2015.
- The ratio of net profit to total advances which was 0.65 per cent in 2014 and 0.97 per cent in 2015. The total advances of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd have increased from Rs. 118.39 crores in 2011 to Rs.140.59 crores in 2015.
- The interest incomes of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd were increased from Rs.18.55 crores in 2011 and Rs.29.61 crores in 2015. The ratio of interest income to total advances was 14.22 per cent in the year 2012 and 21.06 per cent in the year 2015.

Suggestions

- To improve the profit and profitability position, the bank should take necessary initiative to reduce the high cost (Term Deposit). On the other hand it should take necessary initiative to increase the low cost deposit. The low cost deposits consist of Current Account and Savings Bank Deposits. It is otherwise known as CASA deposits.
- As a part of financial inclusion steps may be taken by the bank to open No Frills Account and as per the Scheduled UCBs directives the bank should take necessary initiative to convert the existing 'no-frills' accounts into 'Basic Savings Bank Deposit Accounts' and the facilities

provided under Basic Savings Bank Deposit Account (BSBDA) has to be utilized . The details facilities provided under this scheme are given below.

- Modern technologies like ATM, Core Banking, and Anywhere Banking and so on should be introduced to improve the quality of services in all spheres of banking activities.
- To attract more customers the bank should bring more innovation and creativity in its deposits and loans products in general and the products relating to women and senior citizen in particular.
- To improve the profit and profitability position the Non-SLR investment has to be increased to the maximum possible limit as prescribed by the Scheduled UCBs.
- Scheduled UCBs should prepare a model scheme for granting loans. This scheme should include each and every aspect, which the bank is normally expected to look into which processing loan applications.

Conclusion

Profitability performance ratio of George Town Cooperative Bank Ltd is calculated. All the economic variables of profitability are taken into accounts which influence the profit of Scheduled UCBs in India. Almost in all cases the ratios were in a decreasing trend.

References

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